

From Architecture to Action: Implementing and Validating a Digital Twin for PV Systems Using Real-Time IoT Data

Abstract—This paper presents the development and validation of a Digital Twin (DT) framework for photovoltaic (PV) systems using real-time data acquired through Internet of Things (IoT) devices. The proposed DT integrates sensor-based physical data acquisition with MATLAB-based simulation environments to enable virtual modeling, monitoring, and analysis of PV system performance. A miniature PV setup was instrumented with voltage, current, temperature, and irradiance sensors connected to an Arduino Mega and ESP8266 module for wireless data transmission to the ThingSpeak IoT platform. Three virtual modeling approaches—Simulink-based temperature-enhanced models, PV Array block models, and Simscape Electrical representations—were developed and tested using real-time data as inputs. The performance of each DT model was evaluated by comparing simulated outputs to measured physical values using root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and correlation coefficients. Although all models followed the general output trend, the Simulink-based model with temperature compensation achieved the lowest RMSE in current (0.294 A) and power (11.201 W). This study demonstrates the feasibility and accuracy of real-time DT frameworks for PV systems, offering a low-cost, scalable solution for condition monitoring, diagnostics, and future predictive maintenance applications.

Keywords— *Digital twin, photovoltaic System, ThingSpeak, MATLAB Simulink, real-time validation, IoT, Real-Time Monitoring, Performance Analysis.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The increase of the use of PV systems due to the urgency for the climate change and the global shift of using sustainable energy resources, has caused the widespread deployment of Photovoltaic systems. However, as PV installations become more decentralized and exposed to environmental variability, there is an increasing need for advanced monitoring, diagnostics, and predictive maintenance strategies. In this context, Digital twin (DT) technology offers the optimal solution as they emerge as a transformative tool for optimizing PV performance, reducing downtime, and enhancing energy yield, where it offers real-time virtual replicas of the physical system this to enhance operational efficiency and predictive maintenance capabilities [1].

Originally the DT was conceptualized in the aerospace and manufacturing industries [2], it recently gained traction in the energy sector, particularly for renewable energy systems such as solar photovoltaic installations [3]. Implementing a functional DT for PV systems requires seamless integration of real-time sensor data, communication infrastructure, data analytics, and physics-based modeling to create a dynamic self-updating model that reflects the behavior of the real system. This model not only allows for real-time monitoring but also supports long-term performance analysis and operational forecasting. As PV installations grow in complexity, intelligent DT frameworks that combine physical and data-driven modeling have been introduced [4]. The

integration of the DT technology into the Internet of Things (IoT)-based energy systems offers a novel approach to improving resource management, sustainability, and operational efficiency [5].

Many studies have introduced the advantages of developing a DT for PV systems, as they improve decision-making and operational efficiency [6], despite these advancements there are significant challenges such as high implementation costs and the lack of standardized frameworks across the industry. Moreover, although interest in PV-focused DT is rapidly growing, many existing studies remain largely conceptual or rely on idealized simulation environments, often lacking validation against real-world operational data.

To address this gap, this paper presents a practical framework for a fully implemented and validated DT for a photovoltaic system, bridging the gap between theoretical architecture and actionable insights, using real-time IoT sensor data transmitted via ThingSpeak. The DT framework includes a physical PV system with an Arduino-based sensing module that collects irradiance, temperature, voltage, and current data. These measurements are transmitted to the cloud platform and ingested by MATLAB-based models to simulate power output and assess system performance in real-time.

II. PV DIGITAL TWIN ARCHITECTURE

The DT is the virtual representation of the physical system that continuously shows the condition of the system in real time, where it reflects the status, behavior, and performance. It integrates the real-world sensor data with simulation, modeling, and analytics to enable monitoring, diagnostics, and predictive maintenance. In the context of the PV systems, the DTs are valuable for optimizing energy production, detecting faults, and enabling real-time adaptation to environmental conditions [7], [3]. The proposed DT system for PV systems follows a layered architecture, that combines physical sensing, IoT communication, virtual modeling and analytics

A. Layered Architecture Design

First, the system consists of 5 functional layers, inspired by the established DT framework in energy and cyber-physical systems [8], [9]:

1) Physical Layer

This layer consists of a physical 1.5W standalone PV panel equipped with sensors to capture environmental and electrical parameters:

- Irradiance sensor (TEMT6000)
- Temperature sensor (DHT11)
- Voltage and current sensors (voltage divider sensor 25 V and ACS712 5 A.)

These sensors are connected to an Arduino Mega 2560 that collects the raw data.

2) Data Acquisition and Communication Layer

Sensor data is transmitted to the cloud in near real-time via an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module. The ThingSpeak IoT platform is used to log and visualize the data. Data points are updated at fixed intervals (every 10 minutes) and include time-stamped values of voltage, current, irradiance, and temperature.

3) . Virtual Modeling Layer

At this layer, the DT receives real-time irradiance and temperature values and simulates PV system behavior using three modeling approaches developed in MATLAB/Simulink:

- Simulink PV Block Model: Uses MATLAB's PV Array block with irradiance and temperature inputs.
- Simscape Electrical Model: Implements physical components (diodes, resistors, current sources) to simulate electrical behavior.
- Improved MATLAB Function Model: A custom single-diode model with temperature compensation, developed using a MATLAB Function Block.

All models receive live data from ThingSpeak and output simulated current, voltage, and power values.

4) Service & Analytics Layer

The core function of this layer is model validation. The outputs of the simulation models are compared to actual ThingSpeak data using statistical metrics:

- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
- Mean Absolute Error (MAE)
- Correlation Coefficient (r)

5) Visualization Layer

The final layer consists of MATLAB plots and dashboards that display:

- Time-series comparisons of simulated vs. measured data,
- Real-time tracking of deviations,
- Error metrics for model tuning and refinement.

This enables users to monitor system performance in near real-time and identify performance issues or anomalies early.

B. Data Flow and System Integration

Figure 1 illustrates the end-to-end data flow between the physical system, IoT platform, modeling environment, and validation process. The ThingSpeak platform serves as the communication bridge between the physical and virtual systems. MATLAB acts as the central processing engine, responsible for ingesting live data, executing simulations, and generating analytics.

Fig. 1. Layered System Architecture of the Digital Twin for PV Systems

III. METHODOLOGY

This study follows a systematic approach to design, implement, and validate a Digital Twin (DT) framework for a photovoltaic (PV) system. The methodology consists of three key stages: (1) real-time data acquisition via IoT, (2) development of a physics-based simulation model in Simulink/Simscape, and (3) performance evaluation through statistical comparison, as shown in Fig. 2. The complete setup for the DT system.

Fig. 2. The complete Setup of the Digital twin system

A. Real-Time Data Acquisition via IoT

To enable live monitoring of PV system behavior, a low-power, low-cost sensing and communication setup was deployed. A 1.5W SOLCHARGE01 PV panel was instrumented with:

- A voltage sensor (connected to analog input A3)
- A current sensor (connected to analog input A2)
- A TEMT6000 irradiance sensor and a temperature sensor

The sensors were connected to an Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller, which relayed the data through an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module to the ThingSpeak cloud platform at 10-minute intervals. This IoT architecture ensured continuous real-time data logging of the PV system's environmental and electrical parameters., as shown in Fig.3, with the detailed sensors connectivity wiring

Fig. 3. Detailed sensors wiring

B. Physics-Based Modeling

Three modeling approaches were implemented in MATLAB/Simulink to serve as the virtual representation of the PV system:

a) Simulink Block-Based Model

As shown in Fig. 4, the model utilized the built-in Simulink PV module (PV Array block) with parameter adjustments based on panel datasheets and measured inputs.

Fig. 4. Simulink Block-Based Model

b) Simscape Electrical Model

In Fig. 5, the created model used Simscape components to model the electrical behavior of the PV system, using measured temperature and irradiance as inputs.

Fig. 5. Simscape Electrical Model

c) Custom MATLAB Function Model

Implements a modified single-diode equation using a MATLAB function block, offering tunable fidelity and faster simulation. Temperature compensation was included.

To ensure accurate simulation and modeling, the electrical characteristics of the Sol-CHARGE01 1.5W PV panel were obtained from the datasheet and used across all models. The key parameters are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE I. PV PANEL ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Maximum power	1.5 W
Maximum Module Voltage (V_{mp})	12 V
Maximum Module Current (I_{mp})	0.125 A
Cell per module (N_{cell})	60
Open circuit voltage (V_{oc})	14.4 V
Short-circuit current (I_{sc})	0.14 A
Parallel strings	1
Series – connected modules per string	1

C. Performance Evaluation Metrics

The fidelity of the DT models was validated by comparing simulation outputs with the real measurements from ThingSpeak. Three statistical error metrics were used:

- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^{sim} - y_i^{meas})^2}$$

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE):

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i^{sim} - y_i^{meas}|$$

- Pearson Correlation Coefficient (Corr):

$$Corr = \frac{cov(y_i^{sim}, y_i^{meas})}{\sigma_{sim} \cdot \sigma_{meas}}$$

Where, n is the number of data point, y^{sim} is the simulated value(Current/Voltage/Power) y^{meas} , is the measured value, cov is Covariance, and σ is the standard deviation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To evaluate the fidelity of the DT system in replicating real-world PV system behavior, we conducted a comparative analysis between simulated and measured data. The results of the three models are showed in Table II, Table III, Table IV ., where showed the errors metrics of the evaluation

TABLE II. METRICS FOR SIMULINK-BASED PV MODEL

Value	Metrix for Using PV Simulink		
	RMSE	MAE	Corr
Current	0.388 A	0.373 A	-0.24
Voltage	24.055 V	24.043 V	0.97
Power	11.231 W	11.016 W	-0.08

The Simulink model exhibited high voltage accuracy with a strong correlation of 0.97. This suggests that the built-in Simulink PV block effectively captures voltage behavior, even under varying irradiance and temperature inputs, it is suitable for scenarios focused on MPPT algorithm validation or grid interface studies.

TABLE III. METRICS FOR SIMSCAPE ELECTRICAL MODEL

Value	Metrix for Using Simscape		
	RMSE	MAE	Corr
Current	0.467 A	0.458 A	-0.01
Voltage	24.140 V	24.127 V	0.53
Power	11.239 W	11.024 W	-0.02

The Simscape model showed consistent RMSE and MAE values across parameters but with mixed correlation, implying model mismatch with actual dynamic behavior.

TABLE IV. METRICS FOR IMPROVED PARAMETERS

Value	Metrix for improved parameters		
	RMSE	MAE	Corr
Current	0.294 A	0.271 A	0.00
Voltage	23.953 V	23.940 V	-0.05
Power	11.201 W	10.984 W	-0.00

The improved parameter model achieved the lowest error metrics in terms of current and power predictions

Fig. 6 displays the real-time current and voltage measurements acquired from the ThingSpeak platform, reflecting actual PV system behavior under varying environmental conditions.

Fig. 7, Fig.8, and Fig. 9 offer visual comparisons between the measured data from ThingSpeak, and the simulated outputs generated by the three different PV models:

Fig. 6. Real-time data acquired from the ThingSpeak cloud platform, including current (A), voltage (V) and Power (W) from the PV system.

The performance of the classic Simulink block-based model, showing the simulated current, voltage, and power alongside the real data, as well as the corresponding error metrics is given by Fig.7.

Fig. 7. Comparison between measured and simulated PV system output using the Simulink model: (a) current, (b) voltage, and (c) power.

The results from the Simscape Electrical model are given by Fig.8.

Fig. 8. Comparative Plots of Simulated vs. Real PV Output for Simscape model.

And the output of the improved parameter model, which uses refined parameter tuning to better match the real-world measurements, is illustrated in Fig.9.

Fig. 9. Comparative Plots of Simulated vs. Real PV Output for Improved parameters model.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

After This study presented a complete implementation and validation of a DT framework for a photovoltaic (PV) system, integrating real-time IoT data acquisition with multiple MATLAB-based simulation models. By leveraging low-cost sensors, the ESP32 microcontroller, and the ThingSpeak platform, real-world PV parameters such as voltage, current, irradiance, and temperature were continuously monitored and compared with simulated outputs from three different models: a custom improved mathematical model, a standard Simulink PV block model, and a Simscape Electrical physical model.

Performance evaluation using RMSE, MAE, and correlation metrics revealed that:

- The custom mathematical model offered the lowest RMSE and MAE values for current and power predictions.
- The Simulink model demonstrated the highest voltage correlation with real measurements (0.97), indicating strong consistency in voltage simulation.

- The Simscape model, while detailed in physical behavior, required further calibration to improve current and power accuracy.

These findings demonstrate the feasibility of deploying a low-cost, real-time digital twin for small-scale PV systems and underscore the importance of selecting appropriate simulation models based on the intended application—whether for voltage prediction, power tracking, or diagnostic accuracy.

Future research will explore integrating intelligent correction algorithms (e.g., machine learning layers), expanding the DT framework to include storage systems and MPPT control, and scaling the approach for larger PV installations, also future expansion may involve long term DT behavior evaluation as discussed by Luer et al. [10] for organic PV degradation.

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